

Title: The Rise and Rise of Service Robotics. Policies and Guidelines for the Chief Robotics Officer.

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INTRODUCTION:

The application of Service Robotics in business sectors such as Education, Healthcare, and Retail are moving from the innovators to the early adopter phase - expected to rise to a value of US\$ 23.1 billion for the period 2016-2019. This paper explores the policy and guideline implications for organisations that plan to utilise service robots to automate and augment their business activities. Impacts will include the emergence of new disruptive business models.

AIM:

To develop and articulate a strategy for adoption and a framework of governance for optimizing the application of Service Robotics at scale in organizations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study reflects a literature analysis of the rise of service robotics as well as interviews and discussions with CEOs and executive business leaders. It also includes qualitative anecdotal experiential support from Exaptec as a market leader providing Service Robotics solutions in Australia since 2015.

RESULTS:

This study presents a responsibility framework covering legal, ethical and other factors for the productive utilization of Service Robotics that would benefit the organization and clients on a broad front of implications.

CONCLUSIONS:

The adoption of Service Robotics will present many changes, risks and opportunities that will require a responsible governance and management framework. It is also proposed that a position of Chief Robotics Officer (CRO) be created to lead governance and optimise opportunities and deflect risks.

KEYWORDS:

Service Robotics, Chief Robotics Officer, Governance, Policy

BIOGRAPHY:

Nicci Rossouw is the founder and CEO of Exaptec, a start-up company that provides service robotics solutions to the Australian market. She is passionate about applying innovative

technology including artificial intelligence and automation to improve work-life balance and wellness. Nicci believes that well designed application of robotics will lead to the emergence of new business models that will change, for the better, the way people work and play. She is also a leader in enhancing wellness through sport as Board President of Squash and Racquetball Victoria. She immigrated to Australia twenty years ago from South Africa, has two adult sons and lives on a mountain outside Melbourne with an old blind Pomeranian, two chickens, a parrot and a husband.